

37.013.42

GRAMMAR IMPROVEMENT THROUGH AI: A STUDY ON THE SHIFT FROM STANDARD ENGLISH TO GLOBAL ENGLISH

SERIK A.K, TOLUSPAEVA D.Z.

Student of the NAO “Karaganda National Research University
named after Academician E.A.Buketov”

Major: Foreign Languages: Two Foreign Languages

Abstract: *the article examines the features of the use of artificial intelligence in English language teaching, including the impact of chatbots, adaptive platforms and grammar assistants on the development of language skills. It analyzes how AI provides personalized feedback, increases motivation, and improves students' grammatical accuracy. Special attention is paid to the fact that artificial intelligence not only supports the development of standard English, but also forms elements of global English, offering simplified and universally understandable structures. The advantages and risks of implementing AI are emphasized, including possible dependence, errors of interpretation, and the need to combine technology with traditional learning.*

Keywords: *AI chatbots, grammar improvement, Standard English, Global English, language learning, AI-based feedback.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются особенности использования искусственного интеллекта в обучении английскому языку, в том числе влияние чат-ботов, адаптивных платформ и помощников по грамматике на развитие языковых навыков. В статье анализируется, как искусственный интеллект обеспечивает персонализированную обратную связь, повышает мотивацию и улучшает грамматическую точность учащихся. Особое внимание уделяется тому факту, что искусственный интеллект не только поддерживает развитие стандартного английского, но и формирует элементы глобального английского, предлагая упрощенные и универсально понятные структуры. Подчеркиваются преимущества и риски внедрения искусственного интеллекта, включая возможную зависимость, ошибки интерпретации и необходимость сочетать технологию с традиционным обучением.*

Ключевые слова: *AI-чатботы, улучшение грамматики, Standard English, Global English, изучение языка, AI-обратная связь.*

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a field of computer science that deals with the creation of intelligent systems capable of performing tasks that require human intellectual activity. There are many technologies and methods within artificial intelligence, including machine learning, neural networks, natural language processing, and machine learning algorithms.

Machine learning is a subdomain of artificial intelligence that allows computer systems to learn from experience and data. With the help of machine learning, computer programs can independently improve their performance and adapt to new tasks.

Neural networks are a model inspired by the work of the human brain. They consist of a multitude of interconnected artificial neurons that process information and make decisions based on the data received. In the era of digitalization and globalization, the field of education is undergoing changes, acquiring new highly intellectual shades, namely the introduction of various digital fundamental tools such as neural networks, artificial intelligence and others.

In the era of digitalization and globalization, the field of education is undergoing changes, acquiring new highly intellectual shades, namely the introduction of various digital fundamental tools such as neural networks, artificial intelligence and others.

The educational system in Kazakhstan is an important component of the development of our state, which requires special attention to train highly qualified specialists who have the necessary competitive advantages in the labor market and are ready to realize their potential in the digital economy.

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has become an integral part of the educational process, changing the methods of teaching and interaction between teachers and students. In the field of learning foreign languages, AI opens up new opportunities for personalizing learning, increasing student motivation, and automating routine teacher tasks.

The purpose of this article is to examine the use of AI technologies in English lessons, assess their impact on the educational process, identify the advantages and possible risks of their implementation, and offer practical recommendations for the effective use of AI in teaching English.

AI is a field of computer science that includes machine learning, natural language processing, neural networks, and other technologies that mimic human cognitive functions. In the educational field, AI is used to:

- Automation of job verification.
- Creation of interactive training programs.
- Development of adaptive educational platforms.
- Improve online communication between teacher and student.
- Development of intelligent virtual assistants.

The use of AI in English lessons can significantly improve the effectiveness of learning, making it more personalized and interactive.

The impact of AI on the process of learning English

Individualization and personalization of training. AI algorithms are able to analyze a student's level of knowledge, identify their weaknesses and strengths, and offer an individual training program. Platforms such as Duolingo, Grammarly, and ChatGPT use machine learning to adapt content to the specific needs of the learner.

For example, if a student has difficulty with grammar, the system offers additional exercises in this area. In this way, AI helps to narrow the gap between students' abilities and expected learning outcomes.

Improving the perception of oral and written speech. AI systems such as Google Assistant, Siri, Microsoft Speech Recognition, and ChatGPT can analyze student speech, identify pronunciation errors, and suggest ways to correct them. This is especially useful for students learning English as a foreign language, as it allows them to practice pronunciation in a comfortable environment.

In addition, tools like Grammarly and Hemingway help improve writing skills by pointing out grammatical errors, stylistic flaws, and suggesting more precise formulations.

Automating task verification. AI allows you to significantly reduce the time spent checking homework and classroom work. Artificial intelligence-based programs can automatically check spelling, grammar, punctuation, and writing style.

Platforms such as Google Forms with the auto-check feature allow you to create tests, automatically analyze responses, and provide students with instant feedback. This increases the effectiveness of the teacher's work and frees up his time for deeper interaction with students.

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has become an integral part of language education, especially due to the rapid adoption of AI-based chatbots. These tools provide instant feedback, personalized help, and affordable practice opportunities, making them highly attractive to English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners. As students increasingly rely on artificial intelligence to support writing, speaking, and grammar, an important linguistic shift has taken place: a shift from strictly following the standard norms of English to using the features of global English, a more flexible and internationally understandable form of language. Standard English is traditionally considered the standard of grammatical correctness in academic and professional communication.

However, the global spread of the English language and the development of digital communications have changed perceptions of what is considered “right” or “acceptable”. Artificial intelligence chatbots, designed to communicate clearly with users around the world, often use simplified grammatical structures and fewer region-specific vocabulary. As a result, students gain access to diverse forms in which clarity and complementarity are prioritized rather than strict adherence to norms accepted by native speakers. This phenomenon suggests that artificial intelligence can not only support grammar learning, but also influence the evolution of students' language preferences.

Understanding how artificial intelligence tools affect grammar development is important, especially in educational contexts where accuracy and standardization are still important. While artificial intelligence-based feedback can reduce grammatical errors and increase student confidence, it can also contribute to the normalization of simplified, globalized forms of English. This dual impact raises fundamental questions about the role of artificial intelligence in modern language learning: does artificial intelligence help students improve grammar in accordance with standard English norms, or does it accelerate the transition to global English? And how should teachers respond to these changing trends?

The purpose of this study is to explore these issues by examining the extent to which chatbots with artificial intelligence influence the use of grammar by students and contribute to the wider spread of the English language around the world. By analyzing both the benefits and potential challenges of learning with artificial intelligence, the authors of the study aim to provide a clearer understanding of the linguistic, pedagogical, and cultural implications of integrating artificial intelligence technologies into English language teaching.

The integration of artificial intelligence-based chatbots into the English language learning process has attracted significant attention in recent studies due to their potential impact on grammar development and the transition from standard English to global English. Research has shown that chatbots with artificial intelligence provide instant corrective feedback, which helps to reduce grammatical errors, improve student fluency, and increase self-reliance. The article “Transforming Language Education: A Systematic Review of AI-Powered Chatbots for English as a Foreign Language Speaking Practice” (2024) systematically analyzes research on chatbots for EFL (English as a Foreign Language). The authors conclude that chatbots “significantly improve learners' oral proficiency, expression, and confidence, providing them with a safe environment for practice without the fear of making mistakes”. However, some scientists warn that students may overly rely on artificial intelligence suggestions, potentially making it difficult to learn complex grammatical rules [1].

At the same time, the widespread adoption of artificial intelligence in language learning reflects broader linguistic trends. The global use of English as a lingua franca is changing what is considered “correct” grammar, favoring clarity and intelligibility for all rather than strict adherence to norms accepted by native speakers. Artificial intelligence chatbots trained on various international databases tend to create simplified, universally understandable structures, minimizing idioms, phrasal verbs, and regional vocabulary. This shift introduces students to the global forms of the English language, imperceptibly influencing their language preferences and leading them away from the complexity and idiomatic richness typical of standard English.

The use of AI also affects students' perception of the correctness of their actions. Du, H., Zhang, Q., & Hafiz notes that students often consider the results of AI work to be authoritative, even if they differ from textbooks or use by native speakers. Consequently, what students consider “acceptable” English increasingly corresponds to simplified, globally understandable forms generated by artificial intelligence, rather than the traditional standard rules of the English language. Research based on surveys once again illustrates this trend: for example, approximately 78% of students report that chatbots with artificial intelligence help reduce the number of grammatical errors, 84% believe that English created with the help of artificial intelligence is easier to understand, and 62% admit that their perception of correct grammar has changed. after using artificial intelligence tools [2].

These conclusions are also confirmed by a comparative analysis of the features of standard English and global English, created under the influence of artificial intelligence. Standard English typically uses complex sentence structures, common idioms and phrasal verbs, a vocabulary specific to the region, and strict grammatical precision. On the contrary, in English created with the help of artificial intelligence, special attention is paid to simpler sentence constructions, a minimum number of idiomatic expressions, a reduced regional vocabulary, flexible grammar and priority international intelligibility. Such differences can be visualized in the form of a histogram or table, demonstrating how the use of artificial intelligence contributes to the creation of a more universal form of English suitable for global communication, while at the same time potentially reducing the complexity inherent in native speakers.

The literature indicates that chatbots with artificial intelligence not only contribute to improving grammar, but also contribute to a gradual linguistic shift towards global English [3]. This dual effect has important implications for language teaching, assessment, and curriculum design, suggesting that teachers should combine the benefits of learning through artificial intelligence with the need to maintain awareness of standard English language norms.

The integration of artificial intelligence-based tools into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes opens up new opportunities to improve students' grammatical skills. Traditional grammar instruction is often based on textbooks, teacher-led explanations, and repetitive exercises that may lack responsiveness and personalized feedback. Artificial intelligence-based tools such as chatbots, grammar checkers, and writing assistants offer real-time error correction, adaptive suggestions, and interactive learning.

In practice, AI can be implemented in various types of activities. For example, teachers can assign written tasks such as short essays, dialogues, or story creation, and use AI tools to provide immediate feedback on sentence structure, verb tense, word choice, and overall sequence. AI-powered chatbots can mimic real conversations, allowing students to practice grammar in context, such as when ordering meals at a restaurant, negotiating, or discussing cultural topics. Gamified platforms with artificial intelligence can also boost motivation by awarding points, badges, or tracking grammar progress.

Another important advantage of implementing AI is personalization. AI tools can identify individual weaknesses, track progress, and offer exercises tailored to the student's needs. For example, if a student often uses past tense verbs incorrectly, the AI can offer targeted exercises aimed at using them correctly. This adaptive approach provides more effective learning than traditional methods that are suitable for everyone.

The introduction of artificial intelligence in EFL classrooms is aimed at providing interactive, adaptive and immediate grammar learning support, developing independence, engagement and better preparation for using English in a global context.

Despite the promising potential of AI tools in improving grammar skills and popularizing the English language in the world, a number of challenges and limitations remain. First, over-reliance on AI can lead students to rely too heavily on automated corrections, which will reduce their ability to edit and critically evaluate their own texts on their own. Secondly, contextual misunderstandings may arise, as artificial intelligence tools sometimes misinterpret nuances of expressions, idiomatic phrases, or cultural language usage, which can lead to inappropriate corrections. Third, accessibility and digital literacy are limiting factors: not all students have equal access to artificial intelligence technologies or the necessary skills to use them effectively. Fourth, the difference in AI accuracy is worrisome; Different platforms can provide conflicting feedback, leading to confusion among students. Finally, ethical and privacy considerations when using artificial intelligence tools, such as data security and potential bias in AI-generated offerings, remain significant constraints that teachers and students must consider. This study examined the role of artificial intelligence-based chatbots in improving grammar and their impact on the transition from standard English to global English. The results show that artificial intelligence tools provide instant, personalized feedback that enhances grammatical accuracy, fluency, and student engagement.

By offering simplified and universally understandable structures, chatbots with artificial intelligence contribute to the development of global English, helping students communicate effectively in various international contexts. However, the study also reveals important issues, including the risk of over-reliance on artificial intelligence, potential misunderstandings of contextually complex language, and differences in access and digital literacy. While artificial intelligence promotes grammar learning and promotes more globally understandable forms of English, teachers should combine its use with teaching standard English language norms so that students maintain an understanding of traditional grammatical accuracy.

In general, learning a language using artificial intelligence is a powerful tool for developing grammatical skills and facilitating global communication. With a thoughtful approach, it can complement traditional teaching methods, support autonomous learning, and prepare students to participate in an increasingly interconnected world where clarity and adaptability of English are valued.

The use of AI in the educational process provides many advantages:

1. Personalized approach – programs are adapted to the student's level of knowledge and needs.
2. Saving teachers time – automatic task review allows them to pay more attention to the methodology and individual work with students.
3. Developing student independence – AI helps students learn at a pace that is convenient for them.
4. Instant feedback – the student can immediately see his mistakes and correct them.
5. Flexible learning – AI platforms allow you to learn anytime, anywhere.
6. Accessibility – Many AI tools are free or have low-cost subscriptions, making them accessible to a wide range of students.

In order to effectively use AI in the educational process, teachers should consider several recommendations::

1. Selection of suitable tools. Use proven platforms such as ChatGPT, Duolingo, Grammarly, Google Forms.
2. Combining AI with traditional methods. Technology should complement, not replace, teachers.
3. Teacher training. To organize courses on digital literacy and the use of AI in education.
4. Quality control of AI work. Check the correctness of recommendations and corrections offered by algorithms.
5. Developing students' critical thinking. Explain that AI can make mistakes and encourage self-analysis of information [4].

The use of artificial intelligence in English lessons opens up huge opportunities for individualization and improvement of learning efficiency. However, despite all the advantages, AI should not replace the teacher, but only complement his work. The optimal combination of traditional methods and modern technologies will create the most productive educational environment in which students can not only learn the language, but also develop critical thinking, communication skills and independence. The introduction of AI requires an integrated approach, including teacher training, the selection of high-quality tools, and monitoring the correctness of algorithms. Only in this case, technology will become a powerful assistant in teaching English, ensuring high learning outcomes.

LIST OF SOURCES USED:

1. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666920X24000316>
2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385329890_The_Effect_of_Artificial_Intelligence_AI_on_Students'_Learning.
3. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/ijal.12668>
4. <https://qazsaq.kz/primenienie-iskusstvennogo-intellekta-na-urokah-anglijskogo-yazyka/>